

Cryptography in Terms of Triangular Neutrosophic Numbers with Real Life Applications

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Abstract

In this article, our main focus is to put forward the concept of Cryptography in terms of triangular neutrosophic numbers. This kind of cryptography is really reliable, manual, secure, and based on few simple steps. All the encryption and decryption are easy to proceed (mention below). As we know, Public-key cryptography as an indefatigable defender for human privacy and use as information transfer from the ages. various concepts are available with regard to cryptography e.g. Elliptic curve cryptography. TNNC (Triangular neutrosophic numbers cryptography) is familiar with basic concepts of math as well as applicable in different situations e.g. code cryptography, detailed view cryptography, and Graph cryptography encryption facilitate.

Keywords: Cryptography, Triangular Neutrosophic numbers, Code Encryption, Detailed overview encryption.

Why is Cryptography in Terms of Triangular neutrosophic numbers required?

- ❖ Easy to use and no computer work required to proceed (Fully manual).
- ❖ With the help of math's law, it is impossible to decrypt without a key.
- ❖ No internet required for that kind of cryptography.
- ❖ Convenient for personal use as well as for personal records.
- ❖ Based on basic math calculation and possible to proceed with one formula.

1 Introduction and History

Analysts, investigators, and mathematicians from all over the world introduce a wide range of techniques to solve decision-making problems. After great approaches in the field of medicine, selection problem, human resources, and now with the help of Triangular neutrosophic numbers TNNs, new possibilities are available, with respect to cryptography. Researchers give their best, as fundamental of cryptography, principles, applications, and encryption slandered [1-2]. Cryptography has become really handy and image cryptography [3-6], color image cryptography has been introduced [7] and chocolate cryptography also has been developed [8]. Stegano-cryptosystems introduced as well as researchers have also create new approaches in cryptography including S-Boxes [9-19].

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Life is full of uncertainty and decision making, and math is a key to solve daily life problems, on the way to serve humankind. Fuzzy logic has its own importance (introduced by Molodtsov) [20] in 1999 to deal with uncertainty. After the fuzzy set theory [21-23] Intuitionistic fuzzy sets was introduced [24] then neutrosophic sets [25]. Fuzzy and Neutrosophic set theory plays an important role in the field of uncertainty and to handle situation regards to multi-criteria decision making and in the line of evolution, neutrosophic fuzzy numbers [26] and finally Triangular neutrosophic numbers were introduced [27].

Figure 1

Researchers also exaggerate the concept of neutrosophic [28-40]. Neutrosophic sets, which we use, are based on truth, indeterminacy, and falsity. Wang [41] introduces Single-value neutrosophic sets and Ye [42] further furnished the concept of neutrosophic sets. Smarandache and many other researchers [43-50] introduce TOPSIS technique and their services in multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM), also appreciable. As well as many other researchers from different origins of the world introduce many possibilities and put forward the concept of Multi-Criteria decision-making (MCDM) [51-57] and the properties of triangular and pentagonal neutrosophic number are proposed by A. Chakraborty [58-59].

UP until the 1970s, Encryption all over the world was based on symmetric ciphers, after that technology rises and overcomes Manual Cryptography methods. But remember that, online cryptography is risky and complex in some situations. Hence by TNNC Manual cryptography is simple to use secure, undemanding and Cipher Text is now more complex and impossible to break. With huge applications in code encryption, name encryption and complete information of the company is now secure manually.

1.1 Motivation and Benefits

As we all know that, neutrosophic is advance universe and really convenient to solve MCDM problems and now introduces new possibilities in Cryptography. With the help of Triangular Neutrosophic concept manual cryptography resurrect as well as, with more security, less demanding and easy steps to occur. This concept is totally new, Cipher text is now more complex, deal with truth, indeterminacy and falsity at the same time, Graph Encryption possible and with one key this cryptography is now personal cryptography. Hence, all the personal records (Account number, budget, earning, Persons for different situations, Graphs) are all Encrypted manually.

1.2 The Paper Presentation

In this current epoch, the concept of manual Cryptography as TNNC is extended.

- ❖ Formation of Triangular Neutrosophic numbers Cryptography (TNNC) with detailed algorithm.
- ❖ Code Encryption as well as complete bank accounts encryption with budget amount.

- ❖ Name of Persons for different situation also encrypted.
- ❖ Complete company data encrypted manually.

1.3 Structure of Paper

The article depends upon these following prospective.

2 Mathematical Definitions

Definition 2.1: Neutrosophic set: Set \tilde{nA} is neutrosophic if $\tilde{nA} = \{ \tilde{x}; [\tilde{T}_{\tilde{nA}}(\tilde{x}), \tilde{I}_{\tilde{nA}}(\tilde{x}), \tilde{F}_{\tilde{nA}}(\tilde{x})] : \tilde{x} \in \tilde{X} \}$, where $\tilde{T}_{\tilde{nA}}(\tilde{x}) \mapsto [0,1]$, $\tilde{I}_{\tilde{nA}}(\tilde{x})$ and $\tilde{F}_{\tilde{nA}}(\tilde{x})$ are membership functions of truth, indeterminacy and falsity with this following relation:

$$0^- \leq \tilde{T}_{\tilde{nA}}(\tilde{x}), \tilde{I}_{\tilde{nA}}(\tilde{x}), \tilde{F}_{\tilde{nA}}(\tilde{x}) \leq 3^+$$

Definition 2.2: Triangular Neutrosophic Numbers: Single-value Triangular neutrosophic number is given as $\tilde{A}_{\tilde{Neu}} = (\tilde{p}_1, \tilde{p}_2, \tilde{p}_3; \tilde{r}_1, \tilde{r}_2, \tilde{r}_3)$ and their truth, indeterminacy and falsity membership is given as:

$$\tilde{T}_{\tilde{A}_{\tilde{Neu}}}(\tilde{x}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\tilde{x} - \tilde{p}_1}{\tilde{p}_2 - \tilde{p}_1} & \text{for } \tilde{p}_1 \leq x < \tilde{p}_2 \\ 1 & \text{when } \tilde{x} = \tilde{p}_2 \\ \frac{\tilde{p}_3 - \tilde{x}}{\tilde{p}_3 - \tilde{p}_2} & \text{for } \tilde{p}_2 < x \leq \tilde{p}_3 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\tilde{I}_{\tilde{A}_{\tilde{Neu}}}(\tilde{x}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\tilde{q}_2 - \tilde{x}}{\tilde{q}_2 - \tilde{q}_1} & \text{for } \tilde{q}_1 \leq x < \tilde{q}_2 \\ 0 & \text{when } \tilde{x} = \tilde{q}_2 \\ \frac{\tilde{x} - \tilde{q}_2}{\tilde{q}_3 - \tilde{q}_2} & \text{for } \tilde{q}_2 < x \leq \tilde{q}_3 \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\tilde{F}_{\tilde{A}_{\tilde{Neu}}}(\tilde{x}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\tilde{x} - \tilde{p}_1}{\tilde{p}_1 - \tilde{p}_2} & \text{for } \tilde{p}_1 \leq x < \tilde{p}_2 \\ 1 & \text{when } \tilde{x} = \tilde{p}_2 \\ \frac{\tilde{p}_3 - \tilde{x}}{\tilde{p}_3 - \tilde{p}_2} & \text{for } \tilde{p}_2 < x \leq \tilde{p}_3 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where $0 \leq \tilde{T}_{\tilde{A}_{\tilde{Neu}}}(\tilde{x}) + \tilde{I}_{\tilde{A}_{\tilde{Neu}}}(\tilde{x}) + \tilde{F}_{\tilde{A}_{\tilde{Neu}}}(\tilde{x}) \leq 3, \tilde{x} \in \tilde{A}_{\tilde{Neu}}$

Parametric form is defined as: $(\tilde{A}_{\tilde{Neu}})_{\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta}, \tilde{\gamma}} = [\tilde{T}_{\tilde{Neu1}}(\tilde{\alpha}), \tilde{T}_{\tilde{Neu2}}(\tilde{\alpha}); \tilde{I}_{\tilde{Neu1}}(\tilde{\beta}), \tilde{I}_{\tilde{Neu2}}(\tilde{\beta}); \tilde{F}_{\tilde{Neu1}}(\tilde{\gamma}), \tilde{F}_{\tilde{Neu2}}(\tilde{\gamma})]$, where,

$\tilde{T}_{\tilde{Neu1}}(\tilde{\alpha}) = \tilde{p}_1 + \tilde{\alpha}(\tilde{p}_2 - \tilde{p}_1), \tilde{T}_{\tilde{Neu2}}(\tilde{\alpha}) = \tilde{p}_3 - \tilde{\alpha}(\tilde{p}_3 - \tilde{p}_2)$, $\tilde{I}_{\tilde{Neu1}}(\tilde{\beta}) = \tilde{q}_2 - \tilde{\beta}(\tilde{q}_2 - \tilde{q}_1)$, $\tilde{I}_{\tilde{Neu2}}(\tilde{\beta}) = \tilde{q}_2 + \tilde{\beta}(\tilde{q}_3 - \tilde{q}_2)$, $\tilde{F}_{\tilde{Neu1}}(\tilde{\gamma}) = \tilde{r}_2 - \tilde{\gamma}(\tilde{r}_2 - \tilde{r}_1)$, $\tilde{F}_{\tilde{Neu2}}(\tilde{\gamma}) = \tilde{r}_2 + \tilde{\gamma}(\tilde{r}_3 - \tilde{r}_2)$, here $0 < \tilde{\alpha} \leq 1, 0 < \tilde{\beta} \leq 1, 0 < \tilde{\gamma} \leq 1$ and $0 < \tilde{\alpha} + \tilde{\beta} + \tilde{\gamma} \leq 3$.

Definition 2.3: Group is algebraic structure formed by:

- Set with element G.
- Closed operation on set G, as well as associative. Which is $(\tilde{a} \cdot \tilde{b}) \cdot \tilde{c} = \tilde{a} \cdot (\tilde{b} \cdot \tilde{c})$, for $\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}, \tilde{c} \in G$.
- Identity element
- Availability of inverse under set operation

Group which have set operation commutative $(\tilde{a} \cdot \tilde{b} = \tilde{b} \cdot \tilde{a})$ defined as *abelian group*.

Here we have ‘+’ as set operation and ‘0’ as identity element. We gain a valid group by these prospective and by set of integers ‘Z’, where pain of inverse and integers with opposite signs are used. With no inverse natural number ‘N’ does not form a group.

Definition 2.4: With the operation (.) and \tilde{a} be a element of group G with identity 1. Order of \tilde{a} and it is of smallest integer \tilde{n} such that:

$$\frac{\tilde{a} \cdot \tilde{a} \cdot \tilde{a} \dots \tilde{a}}{\tilde{n}} = 1$$

Set $\{\tilde{a}, \tilde{a}^2, \tilde{a}^3, \tilde{a}^4, \dots, \tilde{a}^{\tilde{n}}\}$ compose a cyclic subgroup of G with order \tilde{n} , here \tilde{a} is *generator* for the subgroup.

3 Methodology with Example

Suppose the number in 0.97 as plain Text and the key for encryption is 0.21. The procedure depends upon following steps:

We have three values in Triangular fuzzy numbers.

Step 1

Add the key in second value of set:

$\{0.97, 0.97, 0.97\} \mapsto$ add key (0.21) in second number $\mapsto \{0.97, 1.18, 0.97\}$

Step 2

The three persons are William as ideal person (Truth), Mason as backup (Indeterminacy) and John not recommended for this situation (Falsity). Now convert the names in the form of numbers.

This methodology, consist of one more step: Convert the name into number. For this procedure, Convert the name into less letter. William $\mapsto \check{W}\check{L}\check{M}$, Mason $\mapsto \check{M}\check{S}\check{N}$ and John $\mapsto \check{J}\check{H}\check{N}$. Know by the help of above table entertain them with numerical values. $\check{W}\check{L}\check{M} \mapsto 2.3+ 0.12+ 0.13=2.55$. $\check{M}\check{S}\check{N} \mapsto 0.13+ 0.19+ 0.14=0.46$ and $\check{J}\check{H}\check{N} \mapsto 0.10+ 0.08+ 0.14=0.32$.

Truth	Indeterminacy	Falsity
$\check{A} = \{(2.55, 2.55, 2.55)\}$	$(0.46, 0.46, 0.46)$	$(0.32, 0.32, 0.32)\}$

Let Key = 0.77

Encryption: Add the key in the middle value of all above:

$\check{A} = \{(2.55, 3.32, 2.55)\}$	$(0.46, 1.23, 0.46)$	$(0.32, 1.09, 0.32)\}$
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Apply Formula $\frac{\check{a}_1+\check{b}_1+\check{c}_1}{3}$ and get the result as:

$\check{A} = \{(2.806666667) (0.7166666667) (0.5766666667)\}$ This is the **Cipher Text**.

Decryption: Multiply the Cipher text by 3:

$\check{A} = \{(8.42) (2.15) (1.73)\}$, Now Subtract the key:

$\check{A} = \{(7.65) (1.38) (0.96)\}$, Now divide it by 3:

Truth	Indeterminacy	Falsity
$\check{A} = \{(2.55,2.55,2.55)\}$	$(0.46,0.46,0.46)$	$(0.32,0.32,0.32)\}$

Finally compare the number with name, by the help of table as $\check{W}\check{L}\check{M} \mapsto 2.55$, $\check{M}\check{S}\check{N} \mapsto 0.46$ and $\check{J}\check{H}\check{N} \mapsto 0.32$.

4.3 Case 3: Graph Cryptography

Suppose a person want to be aware of online scam and want to save his personal company information manually. Here, with the help of one single key he can store multiple data manually with few single steps.

a) Progress per 10 days

The progress is 89%, 29% and 69%, on the base of 1000\$. Add zero in front of numbers.

$\check{A} = \{(0.89, 0.89, 0.89)\}$	$(0.29, 0.29, 0.29)$	$(0.69, 0.69, 0.69)\}$
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Let Key = 0.77

Encryption: Add the key in the middle value of all above:

$\check{A} = \{(0.89, 1.66, 0.89)\}$	$(0.29, 1.06, 0.29)$	$(0.69, 1.46, 0.69)\}$
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Apply Formula $\frac{\check{a}_1+\check{b}_1+\check{c}_1}{3}$ and get the result as:

$\tilde{A} = \{(1.146666667) (0.546666667) (0.946666667)\}$ This is the **Cipher Text**.

Decryption: Multiply the Cipher text by 3:

$\tilde{A} = \{(3.44) (1.64) (2.84)\}$, Now Subtract the key:

$\tilde{A} = \{(2.67) (0.87) (2.07)\}$, Now divide it by 3:

$\tilde{A} = \{(0.89, 1.66, 0.89) \quad (0.29, 1.06, 0.29) \quad (0.69, 1.46, 0.69)\}$

b) Budget

Now the most personal thing, need to hide is company budget, for this purpose we just have to follow these following steps. Firstly, convert it in percentage and then encrypt and decrypt it. The percentages are 39% as remaining, 42% and 19% are investment per 15 days.

$\tilde{A} = \{(0.39, 0.39, 0.39) \quad (0.42, 0.42, 0.42) \quad (0.19, 0.19, 0.19)\}$

Let Key = 0.77

Encryption: Add the key in the middle value of all above:

$\tilde{A} = \{(0.39, 1.16, 0.39) \quad (0.42, 1.19, 0.42) \quad (0.19, 0.96, 0.19)\}$

Apply Formula $\frac{\tilde{a}_1 + \tilde{b}_1 + \tilde{c}_1}{3}$ and get the result as:

$\tilde{A} = \{(0.646666667) (0.676666667) (0.446666667)\}$ This is the **Cipher Text**.

Decryption: Multiply the Cipher text by 3:

$\tilde{A} = \{(1.94) (2.03) (1.34)\}$, Now Subtract the key:

$\tilde{A} = \{(1.17) (1.26) (0.57)\}$, Now divide it by 3:

$$\tilde{A} = \{(0.39, 0.39, 0.39) \quad (0.42, 0.42, 0.42) \quad (0.19, 0.19, 0.19)\}$$

c) Earning per 10 days

The progress is 899\$, 299\$ and 699\$

$$\tilde{A} = \{(0.899, 0.899, 0.899) \quad (0.299, 0.299, 0.299) \quad (0.699, 0.699, 0.699)\}$$

Let Key = 0.77

Encryption: Add the key in the middle value of all above:

$$\tilde{A} = \{(0.899, 1.669, 0.899) \quad (0.299, 1.069, 0.299) \quad (0.699, 1.469, 0.699)\}$$

Apply Formula $\frac{\tilde{a}_1 + \tilde{b}_1 + \tilde{c}_1}{3}$ and get the result as:

$$\tilde{A} = \{(1.155666667) (0.555666667) (0.955666667)\}$$
 This is the **Cipher Text**.

Decryption: Multiply the Cipher text by 3:

$$\tilde{A} = \{(3.467) (1.667) (2.867)\}$$
, Now Subtract the key:

$$\tilde{A} = \{(2.697) (0.897) (2.097)\}$$
, Now divide it by 3:

$$\tilde{A} = \{(0.899, 0.899, 0.899) \quad (0.299, 0.299, 0.299) \quad (0.699, 0.699, 0.699)\}$$

Hence, by the help of TNNC, the complete data of company encrypted including progress, budget and earning as well as data depend upon three different parts.

Limitations

- All the calculations are basic and manual, hence image cryptography and sentence encryption are not possible yet.
- All the calculations are in regards to Triangular neutrosophic numbers, so all the codes and values during the process lie between 0 and 3.
- Without the internet but with the help of reliable software like MATLAB, that kind of cryptography is possible and offline apps also developed for this procedure.

5 Conclusion

In this article, our main focus is to promote manual cryptography, which is more secure, less demanding and it is possible to create a personal record with a single key and by least step. All the necessary requirements and limitations of TNNC are also mentioned. Triangular neutrosophic numbers can be used in manual cryptography and now it is possible to create personal record secure manually with a single key. Cypher text is more secure, complex, and impossible to break without a key. The complete procedure of this new concept is available, and all possible personal records in regard to business or for any other condition now encrypted with few simple steps.

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